

APPLYING ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERING AS LITTLE MINIONS: STATISTICAL & COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES TO DAILY ARCHAEOLOGICAL TASKS

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NFDI4Objects
Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

30TH EAA ANNUAL MEETING IN ROME | PERSISTING WITH CHANGE

SAPIENZA UNIVERSITY OF ROME | 28. - 31. AUGUST 2024

SESSION 514 | SATURDAY | 31 AUGUST 2024

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13373890](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373890)

	8:30 - 10:30	11:00 - 13:00	14:00 - 16:00	16:30 - 18:30
Room 37 CU005 FL2 Ponzi I	1091. Archaeology and Nature Management: Friend or Foe? How Archaeological Heritage Is Dealt with in Nature Conservation Context		559. The Mediterranean(s) in Transition: Global Permanence(s), Material Culture(s), and Resilience between 5th and 10th Century AD	
Room 38 CU005 FL2 Ponzi II	975. Baskets and Their Belongings: Archaeobotany and Conservation of Vegetal Basketry Objects and Their Vegetal Content		1138. The Anti-HABI Toolkit: 2nd Workshop on Solutions and Measures for Preventing and Addressing Harassment, Assault, Bullying and Intimidation in Archaeology	
Room 42 CU005 BAS Aula 3	398. What Do Animal Bones Have to Offer? Zooarchaeology and Taphonomy during the Middle to Upper Palaeolithic Transition in Southern Europe		514. Applying Archaeological Research Software Engineering as Little Minions: Statistical & Computational Approaches to Daily Archaeological Tasks	
Room 43 CU013 FL1 Careri	929. 'What Is the Village'? Regional Comparison of Early European and Near Eastern Prehistoric Villages		549. Interdisciplinary Approaches to the Middle Palaeolithic Record of the Balkan Peninsula	
Room 45 CU013 FL1 Conversi	1157. Theoretical and Methodological Definition of the 'Archaeological Potential' in Preventive Archaeology. Challenges and Opportunities		1146. Discovering the Archaeologists of Europe, 10 Years Later	
Room 46 CU013 FL2 Rasetti	654. Centring the object: between production and consumption in ceramic studies		923. Metals and Metalworking I: Compositions and Origin	

14.00-14.15: Introduction

14.15-15.30: 5 Paper

15.30-15.45: Discussion Slot

15.45-16.30: Coffee Break

16.30-17.30: 4 Paper

17.30-18.00: Discussion Slot

AGENDA

COMPUTATIONAL ARCHAEOLOGY

Nowadays computer applications as well as **statistical and computational approaches** constitute a big part of the **toolbox of every archaeologist**, as they open tremendous possibilities for all research.

These can be **ready-to-use (proprietary) software applications** but also "**Little Minions**" (self-scripted tools) or **research software** (e.g. implementation of statistic algorithms in R, Python), which are written by researchers.

COMPUTATIONAL ARCHAEOLOGY AND FAIR4RS

Both, **research software and research data** are part of **Computational Archaeology** and play an important role in up-to-date archaeological research.

Optimally research data (and software) is **FAIR(4RS)** – **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (for Research Software)** – and reproducible of which other users can benefit from or even develop further.

COMPUTATIONAL ARCHAEOLOGY @ CAA

The increasing number of topics and papers at the **international and national chapters of the CAA** show manifold applications but also implications.

Working Groups like the **SIG SSLA** (<https://sslarch.github.io>) or the “**Little Minions**” (<https://littleminions.link>) also deal with Computational Archaeology and are building a community.

LITTLE MINIONS - WHAT IS IT ABOUT?

Part of the **CAA Conference**

Florian Thiery, Ronald Visser, Moritz Mennenga, Brigit Danthine

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**We are the Little Minions -
small self-made scripts,
home-grown small
applications and small
hardware devices - which
help archaeologists in their
daily work.**

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We often reduce the workload or optimise workflows, but we are not often presented to the outside world and the research community.

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Researchers generally focus on presenting the results of research and silently use **Little Minions** to generate these, without not even pointing to them.

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We know, that in
archaeology, research
software is
underrepresented in
conference talks as well as in
research publications.

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Let us promote us as **Little Minions** in the RSE and domain specific research communities to make us visible!

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The Little Minions were created as “Working Group” at the CAA 2018.

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Human helpers organise a session that focus on us **Little Minions** and invite researchers to share their little helpers, so that the scientific community may benefit.

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**We love Open Science and
Open Source Software!**

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Our aim is that all **Little Minions** are non-proprietary as well as open and freely available on e.g. GitHub, GitLab.

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We do give “Minion Talks” which explains the innovative character and mode of operation of the digital tool.

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Stay in contact at
<https://littleminions.link>

DIGITAL HORIZONS:
EMBRACING HERITAGE IN AN EVOLVING WORLD

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Be also part at
CAA 2025 in Athens

COMPUTATIONAL ARCHAEOLOGY @ RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

Several initiatives, such as the **German National Research Data Infrastructure** (NFDI) – especially **NFDI4Objects** – or the **European Open Science Cloud** (EOSC), engage with this topic to **strengthen the position of Computational Archaeologists and Research Software Engineers**, highlight the scientific merit of their work, and ensure researchers receive credit for computational approaches, software development, as well as for writing papers.

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COMPUTATIONAL ARCHAEOLOGY AND SQUIRRELS

Some Little Minions are coded and maintained by independent networks such as the Research Squirrel Engineers Network that maintains, e.g.

- the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin
- Linked Open Ogham Data
- Squirrel Papers

SQUIRREL PAPERS

ASPECTS OF COMPUTATIONAL ARCHAEOLOGY

- treating source code/software as research data
- sharing Little Minions
- discussing challenges in Computational Archaeology
- advancing new algorithms and statistical/computational analysis methods
- (critical) use of AI, discussing pitfalls and complications
- addressing the divide between FAIR(4RS) principles and practices
- incorporating FAIR(4RS) principles into the teaching curriculum
- discussing approaches concerning problems and solutions to legacy data and software
- making complex statistical and computational methods accessible to mainstream archaeology

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2024
28-31 AUG
ROME

**Persisting
with
change**

A stylized map of Rome is depicted using a grid of red and grey squares. A yellow path winds through the map, starting from the top left and ending at the bottom right. A brick wall pattern is visible on the right side of the map.

LET US START!